

Arithmetic control of Wigner–Dyson symmetry classes in kicked Kloosterman maps

Brandon Yates*

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Abstract

This work constructs a family of kicked quantum maps whose Wigner–Dyson symmetry class is controlled by a reflection symmetry of a finite-field kick. The base operator is a self-adjoint Kloosterman Hamiltonian on $\ell^2(\mathbb{F}_q)$: its energy levels are the classical Kloosterman sums and its global level density is the Wigner semicircle. The static evolution is integrable rather than chaotic: its unfolded level statistics are numerically Poisson, its translations are conserved, and its boost-sector out-of-time-order correlator carries an explicit Bessel power-law envelope rather than exponential scrambling. A position kick removes the conserved translations and produces Floquet spectra with random-matrix statistics. For the kick families studied here the symmetry class is selected by an affine-parity criterion: the quadratic kick carries an explicit antiunitary time reversal squaring to $+I$ and lies in the orthogonal class, while the cubic and mixed kicks break the complete affine-coordinate time-reversal family and numerically realize the unitary class. The class assignments are confirmed across prime fields of characteristic greater than three by the adjacent-gap ratio, the spectral form factor, a direct time-reversal residual, and out-of-time-order correlator decay. The construction supplies a finite arithmetic model in which an algebraic property of the kick, rather than a continuous physical coupling, controls Wigner–Dyson universality.

Keywords: quantum chaos · spectral form factor · out-of-time-order correlator · Wigner–Dyson symmetry classes · kicked quantum maps · Floquet systems · random matrix theory

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1 Introduction

This paper constructs a family of kicked quantum maps in which the random-matrix symmetry class of the spectrum is selected by a reflection symmetry of the kick over the finite field. A reflection-symmetric kick carries an antiunitary time-reversal symmetry and places the map in the orthogonal class. For the kicks studied here, a kick that breaks the reflection symmetry removes that time reversal, and its spectral statistics then realize the unitary class. The quadratic kick is reflection-symmetric and the cubic and mixed kicks are not, so the quadratic lies in the orthogonal class and the cubic and mixed in the unitary class. A reflection symmetry of the kick, an arithmetic property of a polynomial over a finite field, thus takes the role usually played by a physical symmetry. The setting is Dyson’s threefold way: when the classical limit of a quantum system is chaotic, the

*Idaho Falls, ID 83404, USA. bmichaelyates@gmail.com.

local fluctuations of its energy levels fall into one of a few universality classes described by random matrix theory, and which class is realized is fixed by the antiunitary symmetries of the system, time reversal and its relatives [1, 2, 4, 5]. The adjustable models for this classification are kicked maps, the kicked rotor and the kicked top, where a free evolution is interleaved with a periodic impulse and the impulse is tuned to move the system between classes [4]. The family presented here replaces the tunable physical impulse with an arithmetic one, and the control parameter for the symmetry class becomes a reflection symmetry over a finite field.

The base of the construction is an exactly solvable arithmetic operator, which we call the Kloosterman Hamiltonian, whose energy levels are the classical Kloosterman sums of analytic number theory and whose level density is the Wigner semicircle. Taken on its own the operator is integrable rather than chaotic: its level statistics are Poisson and its out-of-time-order correlator does not scramble. A position kick removes the integrability and drives the spectrum to random-matrix statistics, after which a reflection symmetry of the kick fixes the class. The transition from integrable to chaotic, and the selection of the chaotic class, are therefore driven entirely by the kick, on top of a single base operator whose spectral theory is fixed throughout by classical theorems, the bound of Weil and the equidistribution of Katz, so the model stays analytically transparent at every step. The construction supplies, in this sense, a discrete arithmetic handle on Wigner–Dyson universality in place of the continuous couplings of the kicked top.

Relation to existing work. The selection of a Wigner–Dyson class by an antiunitary symmetry, and its destruction by a perturbation that breaks that symmetry, is the textbook content of the kicked top and the kicked rotor [4], and the crossover between ensembles in random matrix theory is classical [6, 5]. The present construction introduces neither the symmetry-class mechanism nor the crossover; both are credited to that body of work. The closest finite-dimensional arithmetic dynamical system is the quantized cat map on $\ell^2(\mathbb{Z}/N\mathbb{Z})$ [11, 12], where an arithmetic symmetry reorganizes the spectral statistics through Hecke degeneracy along a subsequence of the inverse Planck constant, a different mechanism acting on a different object. The eigenvalues of the present base operator are Kloosterman sums, whose limiting distribution is governed by the SL_2 geometric monodromy of the Kloosterman sheaf, by the work of Weil, Deligne, and Katz [13, 14, 15]. Quantum access to Kloosterman sums, in the form of a unitary carrying the Kloosterman angles, was raised as a closing open question by Bruin [19], whose own results give a quantum algorithm for computing the sums. The contribution here is the arithmetic control of the symmetry class: the class of the kicked map is selected by a reflection symmetry of the kick over the finite field, reducing for the monomial kicks to their parity, with the orthogonal case established by an explicit antiunitary symmetry theorem.

A physical picture. The free particle on a finite cyclic ring $\mathbb{Z}/d\mathbb{Z}$ is the operator $X + X^{-1}$, where X is the cyclic shift, with the cosine spectrum $2 \cos(2\pi k/d)$ at momentum $k \in \mathbb{Z}/d\mathbb{Z}$ and the additive characters as eigenstates. The Kloosterman Hamiltonian replaces the cyclic ring by a finite field and the bare shift by translations weighted with the phase of the multiplicative inverse, which keeps the additive characters as eigenstates and exchanges the cosine spectrum for the Kloosterman spectrum. The static map is then the free evolution generated by this operator, and the kick is a periodic position-dependent phase, exactly as for the kicked rotor, with the kick polynomial in place of the rotor’s cosine potential.

Section 2 defines the base operator and records its level density. Section 3 establishes that the static map is integrable, through its level statistics and its out-of-time-order correlator. Section 4 introduces the kicked maps, states and proves the antiunitary classification that selects the symme-

try class, and presents the numerical confirmation across prime fields. Section 5 situates the result and records the open questions.

2 The Kloosterman quantum map

Fix a prime power q of characteristic p , and let Tr denote the absolute trace $\mathbb{F}_q \rightarrow \mathbb{F}_p$. Fix once the additive character $\psi(y) = e^{2\pi i \text{Tr}(y)/p}$ of \mathbb{F}_q , so that $\overline{\psi(y)} = \psi(-y)$. The Hilbert space is $\ell^2(\mathbb{F}_q)$, of complex functions on \mathbb{F}_q , with orthonormal position basis $\{|y\rangle : y \in \mathbb{F}_q\}$ and dimension q . The translation operators act by $T_x|y\rangle = |y+x\rangle$, so that $T_x T_{x'} = T_{x+x'}$ and $T_x^\dagger = T_{-x}$.

Definition 2.1 (Kloosterman Hamiltonian). The Kloosterman Hamiltonian is the translation-weighted operator

$$\mathcal{K}_q = \sum_{x \in \mathbb{F}_q^\times} \psi(x^{-1}) T_x \quad (1)$$

on $\ell^2(\mathbb{F}_q)$, the hopping operator whose amplitude for a translation by x is the additive character of the multiplicative inverse x^{-1} .

Proposition 2.2 (Self-adjointness and spectrum). *The operator \mathcal{K}_q is self-adjoint. In the dual (momentum) basis $|a\rangle = q^{-1/2} \sum_{y \in \mathbb{F}_q} \psi(-ay) |y\rangle$, indexed by $a \in \mathbb{F}_q$, it is diagonal,*

$$\mathcal{K}_q |a\rangle = K(a; q) |a\rangle, \quad K(a; q) = \sum_{x \in \mathbb{F}_q^\times} \psi(ax + x^{-1}), \quad (2)$$

with eigenvalues the Kloosterman sums $K(a; q)$. The zero-momentum eigenvalue is $K(0; q) = -1$.

Proof. Taking the adjoint of (1) and using $T_x^\dagger = T_{-x}$ and $\overline{\psi(y)} = \psi(-y)$,

$$\mathcal{K}_q^\dagger = \sum_{x \in \mathbb{F}_q^\times} \psi(-x^{-1}) T_{-x}.$$

Substituting $x \mapsto -x$ and using $(-x)^{-1} = -(x^{-1})$ returns the sum to (1), so $\mathcal{K}_q^\dagger = \mathcal{K}_q$. For the spectrum, $T_x|a\rangle = \psi(ax)|a\rangle$, hence $\mathcal{K}_q|a\rangle = (\sum_{x \neq 0} \psi(x^{-1})\psi(ax))|a\rangle = K(a; q)|a\rangle$. At $a = 0$ the sum is $\sum_{x \neq 0} \psi(x^{-1}) = \sum_{u \neq 0} \psi(u) = -1$, since a nontrivial additive character sums to zero over all of \mathbb{F}_q and hence to -1 over the nonzero elements. \square

The momentum states $|a\rangle$ are the additive characters of \mathbb{F}_q , the analogue of plane waves, so \mathcal{K}_q is diagonalized by the finite Fourier transform and is the finite-field counterpart of a free particle whose dispersion relation is the Kloosterman sum rather than the cosine. The eigenvalues are real by Proposition 2.2; the reality is equivalent to the self-adjointness and reflects that the inversion map $x \mapsto x^{-1}$ is an odd function of x . By (2) each eigenvalue is a sum of roots of unity, hence a real algebraic integer.

Level density. The global distribution of the levels is classical. By the bound of Weil [13],

$$|K(a; q)| \leq 2\sqrt{q} \quad (a \neq 0), \quad (3)$$

so the levels may be written $K(a; q) = 2\sqrt{q} \cos \theta_a$ with $\theta_a \in [0, \pi]$. By the equidistribution theorem of Katz [15] applied to the rank-two Kloosterman sheaf, the ℓ -adic sheaf on the multiplicative group

whose Frobenius traces are the Kloosterman sums and whose geometric monodromy group is SL_2 , the angles $\{\theta_a\}_{a \neq 0}$ equidistribute, as $q \rightarrow \infty$, against the $\mathrm{SU}(2)$ Sato–Tate measure

$$\mu_{\mathrm{ST}}(\theta) = \frac{2}{\pi} \sin^2 \theta d\theta, \quad (4)$$

the equidistribution resting on the purity established by Deligne’s Weil II [14]. Equivalently, the normalized levels $\lambda_a = K(a; q)/\sqrt{q} \in [-2, 2]$ have, in the limit, the Wigner semicircle density

$$\rho_{\mathrm{sc}}(\lambda) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{4 - \lambda^2} \quad (-2 \leq \lambda \leq 2). \quad (5)$$

The semicircle is a global level density and does not constrain the local correlations, which are the proper subject of random-matrix statistics. By the heuristic of Bohigas, Giannoni, and Schmit [2], those local fluctuations track classical chaos rather than the global density, so whether they are of random-matrix or Poisson type is left open by (5) alone. The next section settles it: the global density (5) coexists with integrable, Poisson local statistics.

3 The static map is integrable

The global level density (5) constrains the smoothed distribution of the levels but not their local correlations, and the two are independent. This section establishes that the static Kloosterman map is integrable, by two diagnostics: the local level statistics, which are Poisson, and the out-of-time-order correlator, which does not scramble.

3.1 Poisson level statistics

To probe local correlations the global density must be removed by unfolding. Map each angle through the Sato–Tate cumulative distribution,

$$u_a = \Phi(\theta_a), \quad \Phi(\theta) = \frac{1}{\pi} \left(\theta - \frac{1}{2} \sin 2\theta \right), \quad (6)$$

so that the unfolded levels $\{u_a\} \subset [0, 1]$ have unit mean density. Local statistics are then read from the unfolded nearest-neighbor gaps. A diagnostic insensitive to the unfolding is the adjacent-gap ratio of Oganessian and Huse [7]: for consecutive unfolded gaps s_n , set $r_n = \min(s_n, s_{n+1})/\max(s_n, s_{n+1})$. Its mean takes the value $\langle r \rangle = 2 \ln 2 - 1 \approx 0.386$ for an uncorrelated (Poisson) spectrum, $\langle r \rangle \approx 0.536$ for the orthogonal ensemble, and $\langle r \rangle \approx 0.603$ for the unitary ensemble [8].

Averaged over the prime fields \mathbb{F}_p with $503 \leq p \leq 2203$ (a sample of 22 primes), the unfolded statistics of \mathcal{K}_q are numerically Poisson. The mean gap ratio is $\langle r \rangle = 0.390$, against the Poisson value 0.386 and the unitary value 0.603. The gap variance is 0.959, against the Poisson value 1. The small-gap fractions are $\Pr(s < 0.2) = 0.176$ and $\Pr(s < 0.5) = 0.386$, against the Poisson values 0.181 and 0.393. The spectral form factor, the squared modulus of the Fourier transform of the unfolded level density, sits on the Poisson plateau, with root-mean-square deviation 0.05 from the plateau and 0.55 from the linear ramp of the unitary ensemble. The level-spacing distribution is shown against the Poisson law in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Unfolded nearest-neighbor level-spacing distribution of the static Kloosterman Hamiltonian, aggregated over prime fields, against the Poisson law e^{-s} . The static spectrum has Poisson local statistics despite its semicircle global density.

The semicircle density (5) and the Poisson local statistics are consistent: \mathcal{K}_q is a convolution operator on the additive group, diagonal in a fixed basis of characters by Proposition 2.2, and the absence of level repulsion is the spectral signature of this integrability. The system is an arithmetic calculator whose spectrum carries the global Wigner law but none of the local rigidity of a chaotic system.

The integrability has an operator-algebraic form: the conserved translations form a maximal abelian algebra, contained in the commutant of \mathcal{K}_q and equal to it when the spectrum is simple.

Proposition 3.1 (Commutant of the Kloosterman Hamiltonian). *The translation algebra generated by $\{T_b : b \in \mathbb{F}_q\}$, equivalently the algebra of operators diagonal in the momentum basis, is a maximal abelian subalgebra contained in the commutant of \mathcal{K}_q in the bounded operators on $\ell^2(\mathbb{F}_q)$. The inclusion is an equality if and only if the eigenvalues $\{K(a) : a \in \mathbb{F}_q\}$ are pairwise distinct, in which case the commutant is exactly the translation algebra; in general the commutant is block diagonal over the equal-eigenvalue fibers of $a \mapsto K(a)$.*

Proof. By Proposition 2.2 the operator \mathcal{K}_q is diagonal in the momentum basis with eigenvalue $K(a)$ on $|a\rangle$, and the translations are simultaneously diagonal, $T_b|a\rangle = \psi(ab)|a\rangle$. Since the characters $b \mapsto \psi(ab)$ separate the momenta, the translations span the full momentum-diagonal algebra, which is abelian of dimension q and maximal abelian. An operator commutes with \mathcal{K}_q if and only if it preserves each eigenspace. When the eigenvalues are distinct the eigenspaces are the lines $\mathbb{C}|a\rangle$ and the commutant is exactly this algebra; an equality $K(a) = K(a')$ merges two lines into a plane and enlarges the commutant by the operators mixing them. \square

The translation algebra is abelian, which is what separates genuine integrability from an unresolved symmetry. A nonabelian symmetry would split the spectrum into representation sectors whose unresolved superposition can imitate Poisson statistics, but the irreducible representations of the abelian translation algebra are one-dimensional, so the static spectrum carries no such hidden sector structure. The sporadic equalities $K(a) = K(a')$ are arithmetic, not forced by a symmetry, and too few to assemble into sectors. The Poisson statistics record the abelian integrability of \mathcal{K}_q directly.

3.2 The static map does not scramble

The second diagnostic is the out-of-time-order correlator, which measures the growth of operator complexity under time evolution [9]. The natural unitary operators on $\ell^2(\mathbb{F}_q)$ are the Weyl operators built from the position translations and their momentum-space partners. In the momentum basis the translations act by the phase $T_b|a\rangle = \psi(ab)|a\rangle$, and the momentum shifts, or boosts, act by $M_s|a\rangle = |a-s\rangle$; equivalently M_s is the position-linear phase $\psi(sx)$.

Translations commute with \mathcal{K}_q , since \mathcal{K}_q is itself a combination of translations, so each T_b is a conserved charge of the static evolution and every out-of-time-order correlator built from a translation is time-independent. The dynamics lives in the boost sector. With $M_s(t) = e^{it\mathcal{K}_q} M_s e^{-it\mathcal{K}_q}$ the Heisenberg boost, the infinite-temperature boost-boost correlator is the exact finite- q sum

$$F_{s,s'}(t) = \frac{1}{q} \text{Tr} [M_s(t) M_{s'} M_s(t)^\dagger M_{s'}^\dagger] = \frac{1}{q} \sum_{a \in \mathbb{F}_q} \exp(it \Delta_{s,s'}^2 K(a)), \quad (7)$$

where $\Delta_{s,s'}^2 K(a) = K(a) - K(a-s) - K(a-s') + K(a-s-s')$ is a second difference of Kloosterman sums. The reduction to a single complete exponential sum uses only $M_s(t)|a\rangle = e^{it(K(a-s)-K(a))}|a-s\rangle$, which follows from (2).

The large- q limit reduces the correlator to a moment of independent semicircle variables. For shifts in general position the four are distinct and the envelope is a fourth power.

Proposition 3.2 (Static boost-boost correlator). *Let q be a prime with $q > 3$, and write*

$$\varphi(u) = \int_{-2}^2 e^{iux} \rho_{\text{sc}}(x) dx = \frac{J_1(2u)}{u}$$

for the Fourier transform of the semicircle density (5), with J_1 the Bessel function. Fix $s, s' \in \mathbb{F}_q$ with

$$s \neq 0, \quad s' \neq 0, \quad s + s' \neq 0, \quad s - s' \neq 0,$$

so the four arguments $a, a-s, a-s', a-s-s'$ are distinct, and set $t = \tau/\sqrt{q}$ with τ fixed. Then, as $q \rightarrow \infty$,

$$F_{s,s'}(\tau/\sqrt{q}) \longrightarrow \varphi(\tau)^4 = \left(\frac{J_1(2\tau)}{\tau} \right)^4. \quad (8)$$

Proof. For c in the shift set $C = \{0, s, s', s+s'\}$ the additive translate of the rank-two Kloosterman sheaf with trace function $a \mapsto K(a-c)/\sqrt{q}$ has its single finite singularity at $a = c$. Each such translate carries the geometric monodromy group SL_2 of the Kloosterman sheaf [15], which acts irreducibly and is equal to its own commutator subgroup, and for distinct shifts the singularities are distinct, so no two translates are geometrically isomorphic after twisting by a rank-one sheaf [17, 18]. These are the irreducibility and independence hypotheses of the Goursat–Kolchin–Ribet criterion [16, Prop. 1.8.2], which states that a direct sum of irreducible sheaves with this monodromy, no two related by a rank-one twist, has the full product of their monodromy groups as its geometric monodromy. The criterion therefore gives $\text{SL}_2 \times \text{SL}_2 \times \text{SL}_2 \times \text{SL}_2$ as the geometric monodromy of the direct sum of the four translates; the finitely many exceptional shift values where two singularities collide contribute $O(q^{-1})$ to the normalized average and drop out in the limit. By the equidistribution theorem of Katz [15], resting on Deligne’s Weil II [14], the four normalized levels converge jointly to independent semicircle variables X_0, X_1, X_2, X_3 on $[-2, 2]$. Since the semicircle is symmetric, $\mathbb{E} e^{-i\tau X} = \mathbb{E} e^{i\tau X} = \varphi(\tau)$, and

$$F_{s,s'}(\tau/\sqrt{q}) \longrightarrow \mathbb{E} e^{i\tau(X_0 - X_1 - X_2 + X_3)} = \varphi(\tau)^4,$$

which is (8). □

The exponent four is the count of distinct shifts, and a collision among the shifts merges channels and changes the envelope. The general statement is a product over the distinct shifts, weighted by the multiplicity each carries in the second difference.

Corollary 3.3 (Collision stratification). *For arbitrary $s, s' \in \mathbb{F}_q$, collect equal shifts in $C = \{0, s, s', s + s'\}$ and write*

$$\Delta_{s,s'}^2 K(a) = \sum_c m_c K(a - c)$$

over the distinct values c , where m_c is the sum of the signs $+1, -1, -1, +1$ at $0, s, s', s + s'$ collected at c . Then, as $q \rightarrow \infty$ through primes $q > 3$,

$$F_{s,s'}(\tau/\sqrt{q}) \longrightarrow \prod_c \varphi(m_c \tau), \quad (9)$$

one factor $\varphi(m_c \tau) = J_1(2m_c \tau)/(m_c \tau)$ per distinct surviving shift, omitting any factor with $m_c = 0$. The envelope is fixed by the collision pattern of the shifts. In general position the four are distinct and (9) is the fourth power (8); on the diagonals $s' = \pm s$ with $s \neq 0$ two shifts merge with coefficient of magnitude two,

$$F_{s,\pm s}(\tau/\sqrt{q}) \longrightarrow \varphi(\tau)^2 \varphi(2\tau) = \left(\frac{J_1(2\tau)}{\tau} \right)^2 \frac{J_1(4\tau)}{2\tau}; \quad (10)$$

and if $s = 0$ or $s' = 0$ every coefficient cancels, so $\Delta_{s,s'}^2 K \equiv 0$ and $F_{s,s'} \equiv 1$.

Proof. When the shifts surviving the collision are distinct, the corresponding translates are pairwise non-isomorphic up to a rank-one twist, and the Goursat–Kolchin–Ribet criterion and Katz equidistribution of Proposition 3.2 give joint convergence of the normalized sums $K(a - c)/\sqrt{q}$ to independent semicircle variables X_c . Independence factors the limit,

$$F_{s,s'}(\tau/\sqrt{q}) \longrightarrow \mathbb{E} \exp\left(i\tau \sum_c m_c X_c\right) = \prod_c \mathbb{E} e^{im_c \tau X_c} = \prod_c \varphi(m_c \tau).$$

The named cases follow by collecting equal shifts: the diagonal $s' = s$ leaves $\{0, s, 2s\}$ with coefficients $1, -2, 1$, the anti-diagonal $s' = -s$ leaves $\{0, s, -s\}$ with coefficients $2, -1, -1$, and either vanishing shift leaves every coefficient zero. \square

Example 3.4 (The diagonal shift). For $s = s' = 1$ over \mathbb{F}_q with $q > 3$,

$$\Delta_{1,1}^2 K(a) = K(a) - 2K(a - 1) + K(a - 2),$$

three independent semicircle channels with the middle one carrying coefficient -2 , so $F_{1,1}(\tau/\sqrt{q}) \rightarrow \varphi(\tau)^2 \varphi(2\tau)$ by Corollary 3.3. With $\varphi(u) = 1 - u^2/2 + O(u^4)$,

$$F_{1,1}(\tau/\sqrt{q}) = 1 - 3\tau^2 + O(\tau^4), \quad 1 - \operatorname{Re} F_{1,1} = 3\tau^2 + O(\tau^4),$$

and since $J_1(u) = O(u^{-1/2})$ at large argument, $\varphi(\tau)^2 \varphi(2\tau) = O(\tau^{-9/2})$. The diagonal collision changes the power-law exponent of the envelope but not the conclusion: there is no exponential scrambling window.

For shifts in general position the early-time commutator grows quadratically, $1 - \operatorname{Re} F_{s,s'} = 2\tau^2 + O(\tau^4)$, and the late-time envelope is the power law $(J_1(2\tau)/\tau)^4 = O(\tau^{-6})$; on the collision diagonals the exponents change, as in Example 3.4, but the power-law form does not. There is no exponential growth window in any stratum: the static Kloosterman map has the slow, power-law operator growth of an integrable system, in agreement with its Poisson level statistics. Both diagnostics identify the static operator as integrable, and the next section makes it chaotic by a kick.

4 Arithmetic control of the symmetry class

The kicked map interleaves the free Kloosterman evolution with a periodic position-dependent phase, the kick. For a phase polynomial $h \in \mathbb{F}_q[x]$ let D_h be the diagonal phase operator and $U_{h,\tau}$ the kicked propagator,

$$D_h|x\rangle = \psi(h(x))|x\rangle, \quad U_{h,\tau} = D_h U_{0,\tau}, \quad U_{0,\tau} = e^{-i\tau\mathcal{K}_q/\sqrt{q}}, \quad (11)$$

with τ the free-evolution time. The operator $U_{h,\tau}$ is the one-period Floquet propagator, and its eigenphases carry the spectral statistics of the kicked map. A kick phase is built from a kick polynomial $g \in \mathbb{F}_q[x]$ and a kick strength $\gamma \in \mathbb{F}_q^\times$; for a monomial kick the phase is γg , and we abbreviate $D_\gamma := D_{\gamma g}$ and $U_{\gamma,\tau} := U_{\gamma g,\tau}$. The three kick families studied below are the quadratic kick $g(x) = x^2$ and the cubic kick $g(x) = x^3$, each with phase γg , together with the mixed kick of phase $\gamma x^2 + (\gamma+1)x^3$; the cubic coefficient there is set to $\gamma+1$ so that the cubic term switches off at $\gamma = -1$, where the phase degenerates to the reflection-symmetric $-x^2$ and supplies a within-family orthogonal control point.

4.1 The kick removes the conserved translations

The static evolution is integrable because translations are conserved. The kick removes this conservation precisely when the kick is non-affine.

Lemma 4.1 (Conjugation of translations by the kick). *Let $f \in \mathbb{F}_q[x]$ be a kick phase. For every $b \in \mathbb{F}_q$,*

$$D_f T_b D_f^\dagger = \psi(f(x+b) - f(x)) T_b, \quad (12)$$

where the prefactor denotes the diagonal phase operator $|x\rangle \mapsto \psi(f(x+b) - f(x))|x\rangle$. The right-hand side is a scalar multiple of T_b , and T_b accordingly remains a symmetry of $U_{f,\tau}$ up to a phase, if and only if the phase $\psi(f(x+b) - f(x))$ is independent of x for every b , equivalently if and only if $x \mapsto \text{Tr}_{\mathbb{F}_q/\mathbb{F}_p}(f(x))$ is an affine function over \mathbb{F}_p . Over a prime field, where the trace is the identity, this reduces for a polynomial of degree below p to f being affine in the usual sense. Over a field of prime power order the trace condition is weaker, and a phase of higher polynomial degree can satisfy it: the cubic $f = x^3$ in characteristic three has $\text{Tr}(x^3) = \text{Tr}(x)$, so it is Frobenius-linear and acts as a Weyl boost rather than a non-affine kick.

Proof. Acting on $|x\rangle$, $D_f T_b D_f^\dagger|x\rangle = \overline{\psi(f(x))} D_f|x+b\rangle = \psi(f(x+b) - f(x))|x+b\rangle$, which is (12). Since $\psi(z) = e^{2\pi i \text{Tr}(z)/p}$ depends on z only through $\text{Tr}_{\mathbb{F}_q/\mathbb{F}_p}(z)$, the prefactor is a scalar exactly when $\text{Tr}_{\mathbb{F}_q/\mathbb{F}_p}(f(x+b) - f(x))$ is independent of x , and this holds for every b if and only if $x \mapsto \text{Tr}_{\mathbb{F}_q/\mathbb{F}_p}(f(x))$ is affine over \mathbb{F}_p . Over a prime field the trace is the identity, so for a polynomial of degree below p the condition is $\deg f \leq 1$; the kicks tested over prime fields below, of degree two and three, all fail it. \square

A kick of degree at least two therefore breaks the conserved translations, the maximal abelian symmetry algebra of Proposition 3.1, so the kicked map retains no conserved translation symmetry to resolve and admits genuine spectral statistics. The quadratic, cubic, and mixed kicks all qualify. Which Wigner–Dyson class is realized is the content of the rest of this section.

4.2 The affine-parity antiunitary classification

The symmetry class is fixed by the antiunitary time-reversal symmetries of $U_{\gamma,\tau}$. The natural antiunitaries on $\ell^2(\mathbb{F}_q)$ built from the geometry of the field are the affine coordinate antiunitaries $A_{\alpha,\beta}C$, where C is complex conjugation in the position basis and

$$A_{\alpha,\beta}|x\rangle = |\alpha x + \beta\rangle, \quad \alpha \in \mathbb{F}_q^\times, \beta \in \mathbb{F}_q. \quad (13)$$

Lemma 4.2 shows that static Kloosterman reversibility selects $\alpha = -1$ within this family, so the reversing antiunitaries are exactly the affine-parity involutions

$$R_\beta = A_{-1,\beta}C = T_\beta PC, \quad R_\beta|x\rangle = |\beta - x\rangle, \quad R_\beta^2 = I, \quad (14)$$

with $P|x\rangle = |-x\rangle$ the parity operator. The time-reversal candidate for the kicked map is $\Theta_{f,\beta} = D_f R_\beta$, where f denotes the kick phase.

Lemma 4.2 (Reversing affine coordinate antiunitaries). *Within the family (13), the affine coordinate antiunitary $A_{\alpha,\beta}C$ satisfies $A_{\alpha,\beta}C \mathcal{K}_q (A_{\alpha,\beta}C)^{-1} = \mathcal{K}_q$, and hence reverses the static flow, if and only if $\alpha = -1$. The reversing antiunitaries are therefore exactly the affine-parity involutions $R_\beta = A_{-1,\beta}C$ of (14), for which, with $U_{0,\tau} = e^{-i\tau \mathcal{K}_q / \sqrt{q}}$ the free propagator of (11),*

$$R_\beta U_{0,\tau} R_\beta^{-1} = U_{0,\tau}^{-1} \quad \text{for all } \beta \in \mathbb{F}_q \text{ and } \tau. \quad (15)$$

Proof. Conjugation by C fixes each translation T_s and sends its coefficient $\psi(s^{-1})$ to $\overline{\psi(s^{-1})} = \psi(-s^{-1})$, so $CK_qC^{-1} = \sum_{s \in \mathbb{F}_q^\times} \psi(-s^{-1})T_s$. For the coordinate map, $A_{\alpha,\beta}T_s A_{\alpha,\beta}^{-1}|x\rangle = |x + \alpha s\rangle$, that is $A_{\alpha,\beta}T_s A_{\alpha,\beta}^{-1} = T_{\alpha s}$, independent of β . Hence

$$A_{\alpha,\beta}C \mathcal{K}_q (A_{\alpha,\beta}C)^{-1} = \sum_{s \in \mathbb{F}_q^\times} \psi(-s^{-1}) T_{\alpha s} = \sum_{u \in \mathbb{F}_q^\times} \psi(-\alpha u^{-1}) T_u,$$

where $u = \alpha s$, so that $s^{-1} = \alpha u^{-1}$. Matching the coefficient of each T_u against $\mathcal{K}_q = \sum_u \psi(u^{-1})T_u$ requires $\psi((-\alpha - 1)u^{-1}) = 1$ for all $u \in \mathbb{F}_q^\times$. As u^{-1} ranges over \mathbb{F}_q^\times , this holds for every u only if $-\alpha - 1 = 0$: otherwise $(-\alpha - 1)u^{-1}$ would range over all of \mathbb{F}_q^\times and force ψ to be trivial, against the standing assumption. Hence $\alpha = -1$, and conversely $\alpha = -1$ returns the sum to \mathcal{K}_q . Antiunitarity of R_β then sends i to $-i$, so $R_\beta e^{-i\tau \mathcal{K}_q / \sqrt{q}} R_\beta^{-1} = e^{+i\tau \mathcal{K}_q / \sqrt{q}} = U_{0,\tau}^{-1}$. \square

Theorem 4.3 (Time-reversal criterion). *Let $f \in \mathbb{F}_q[x]$ be the kick phase, so $U_{f,\tau} = D_f U_{0,\tau}$. Then $\Theta_{f,\beta} = D_f R_\beta$ is a time-reversal symmetry, $\Theta_{f,\beta} U_{f,\tau} \Theta_{f,\beta}^{-1} = U_{f,\tau}^{-1}$ for all τ , if and only if*

$$\psi(f(x) - f(\beta - x)) = 1 \quad \text{for all } x \in \mathbb{F}_q, \quad (16)$$

equivalently $\text{Tr}_{\mathbb{F}_q/\mathbb{F}_p}(f(x) - f(\beta - x)) \equiv 0$ for all x . Over a prime field this reads $f(x) = f(\beta - x)$. When the criterion holds, $\Theta_{f,\beta}^2 = +I$, so the time reversal is of orthogonal type.

Proof. The antiunitary conjugates the kick phase and relabels the site through the involution $x \mapsto \beta - x$: a direct computation gives $R_\beta D_f R_\beta^{-1}|y\rangle = \psi(-f(\beta - y))|y\rangle$, that is $R_\beta D_f R_\beta^{-1} = D_{-f(\beta-\cdot)}$. Using Lemma 4.2,

$$\Theta_{f,\beta} U_{f,\tau} \Theta_{f,\beta}^{-1} = D_f (R_\beta D_f U_{0,\tau} R_\beta^{-1}) D_f^{-1} = D_f D_{-f(\beta-\cdot)} U_{0,\tau}^{-1} D_{-f} = D_{f-f(\beta-\cdot)} U_{0,\tau}^{-1} D_{-f}.$$

The target is $U_{f,\tau}^{-1} = (D_f U_0)^{-1} = U_0^{-1} D_{-f}$. The two are equal if and only if $D_{f-f(\beta-\cdot)} = I$, which is (16). For the square, $\Theta_{f,\beta}^2 = D_f (R_\beta D_f R_\beta^{-1}) R_\beta^2 = D_{f-f(\beta-\cdot)} R_\beta^2$, and under (16) the diagonal factor is the identity while $R_\beta^2 = I$, so $\Theta_{f,\beta}^2 = +I$. \square

Corollary 4.4 (Class selection by kick parity). *Over a prime field \mathbb{F}_p with $p > 3$:*

- (i) *the quadratic kick $f = \gamma x^2$ satisfies the criterion (16) at $\beta = 0$, since $f(-x) = f(x)$, so it carries the time-reversal symmetry $\Theta_\gamma = D_\gamma PC$ with $\Theta_\gamma^2 = +I$ and lies in the orthogonal class;*
- (ii) *the cubic kick $f = \gamma x^3$ and the mixed kick $f = \gamma x^2 + (\gamma + 1)x^3$ with $\gamma \neq -1$ break the criterion for every β : the coefficient of x^3 in $f(x) - f(\beta - x)$ is 2γ for the cubic and $2(\gamma + 1)$ for the mixed, both nonzero over \mathbb{F}_p with $p > 3$ since $\gamma \in \mathbb{F}_p^\times$ and $\gamma \neq -1$, so no affine coordinate antiunitary $D_f R_\beta$ reverses the evolution, and the numerical diagnostics of Section 4.3 place the map in the unitary class. At $\gamma = -1$ the mixed phase reduces to $-x^2$, which is reflection-symmetric and orthogonal.*

By Lemma 4.2 the affine-parity involutions R_β exhaust the affine coordinate antiunitaries that reverse the static flow, so part (ii) is the statement that the cubic and mixed kicks break this entire geometric family of time reversals, every member at every β , rather than a single member at $\beta = 0$ or a chosen sub-family. The one antiunitary that survives is inert: any diagonalizable unitary on a finite-dimensional space admits the conjugation fixing its eigenbasis, an antiunitary squaring to the identity, but it depends on the diagonalization and acts on no position, parity, or arithmetic structure, so it carries no constraint on the spectral statistics. The orthogonal assignment in (i) is therefore a symmetry theorem, and the unitary assignment in (ii) rests on the affine coordinate classification of Lemma 4.2 together with the random-matrix statistics reported below.

The named kicks are the degree-two and degree-three cases of a rule that holds at every degree.

Corollary 4.5 (Parity of a monomial kick selects the class). *Let $f = \gamma x^d$ with $\gamma \in \mathbb{F}_p^\times$ over a prime field \mathbb{F}_p with $p > d$. The criterion (16) holds at $\beta = 0$ if and only if d is even, and fails at every β when d is odd. An even-degree monomial kick therefore carries the antiunitary $\Theta_\gamma = D_\gamma PC$ with $\Theta_\gamma^2 = +I$ and lies in the orthogonal class, while an odd-degree monomial kick breaks the affine-parity time-reversal family and is numerically observed here, for $d = 3$ and $d = 5$, to fall in the unitary class. The class is selected by the parity of the degree and not by its size.*

Proof. At $\beta = 0$ the criterion reads $f(x) = f(-x)$, that is $\gamma x^d = (-1)^d \gamma x^d$ for all x , which holds if and only if d is even. For odd d and any β , the coefficient of x^d in $f(x) - f(\beta - x) = \gamma x^d - \gamma(\beta - x)^d$ is $\gamma(1 - (-1)^d) = 2\gamma$, nonzero over \mathbb{F}_p since $p > 2$ and $\gamma \neq 0$; the polynomial $f(x) - f(\beta - x)$ then has exact degree $d < p$ and does not vanish identically, so no β satisfies the criterion. The class assignments follow from Theorem 4.3 as in Corollary 4.4. The hypothesis $p > d$ is necessary: when $p \mid d$ the monomial induces a function of lower degree, the case recorded for the cubic in characteristic three below. \square

The construction is also bounded in which classes it can produce, by the dimension of the Hilbert space.

Corollary 4.6 (Exclusion of the symplectic class). *Over a prime field \mathbb{F}_p with $p > 3$ the Hilbert space $\ell^2(\mathbb{F}_p)$ has odd dimension p , and no antiunitary operator on it squares to $-I$. A symplectic time reversal would have to satisfy $\Theta^2 = -I$ and is therefore excluded, while the explicit geometric antiunitaries constructed above square to $+I$, so the construction realizes the orthogonal and unitary classes but never the symplectic class.*

Proof. Write an antiunitary as $\Theta = WC$ with W unitary and C conjugation in the position basis, so that $\Theta^2 = W\overline{W}$. If $\Theta^2 = -I$ then $W\overline{W} = -I$, and taking determinants gives $|\det W|^2 = \det(W) \det(\overline{W}) = \det(-I) = (-1)^p$, which is -1 for odd p , against $|\det W|^2 \geq 0$. Hence no antiunitary squares to $-I$, and the symplectic class, whose time reversal satisfies $\Theta^2 = -I$, cannot occur. \square

Scope: characteristic three. The cubic kick is studied over prime fields $p > 3$ for a structural reason. Over a field of characteristic three the cubic phase is secretly linear: since the absolute trace satisfies $\text{Tr}(z^3) = \text{Tr}(z)$ and every $\gamma \in \mathbb{F}_{3^r}$ has the cube root $\gamma^{1/3} = \gamma^{3^{r-1}}$, one has $\psi(\gamma x^3) = \psi(\gamma^{1/3} x)$, so $D_{\gamma x^3}$ is the Weyl boost $M_{\gamma^{1/3}}$, an affine kick outside the cubic class by Lemma 4.1. The cubic universality test therefore cannot be run in characteristic three, and prime fields $p > 3$ are the natural setting.

4.3 Numerical confirmation

The class assignments of Corollary 4.4 are confirmed by four diagnostics across the prime fields \mathbb{F}_p with $p \in \{31, 43, 61, 83, 101, 127\}$: the adjacent-gap ratio of the Floquet eigenphases, the spectral form factor, a direct check of the time-reversal residual, and the decay of the out-of-time-order correlator. These fields are smaller than those used for the static statistics of Section 3.1, because each diagnostic requires the full Floquet spectrum of the q -dimensional propagator at every kick strength. Unless stated otherwise the free-evolution time is $\tau = 2.3$ and statistics are averaged over the kick strengths $\gamma = 1, \dots, 16$.

Gap ratio. Table 1 lists the mean adjacent-gap ratio of the Floquet eigenphases for the static map and the three kicks. The static map sits at the Poisson value, the quadratic kick at the orthogonal value, and the cubic and mixed kicks at the unitary value, across the field sizes. Each static entry is a single spectrum of dimension p with no kick strength to average over, so it fluctuates more than the kicked entries averaged over $\gamma = 1, \dots, 16$, which accounts for the low static value at $p = 61$. The values are plotted against q in Figure 2.

p	static	quadratic	cubic	mixed
31	0.373	0.513	0.581	0.608
43	0.388	0.526	0.591	0.602
61	0.327	0.546	0.602	0.601
83	0.384	0.532	0.599	0.603
101	0.397	0.532	0.593	0.601
127	0.410	0.523	0.608	0.590
reference	0.386	0.536	0.603	0.603

Table 1: Mean adjacent-gap ratio $\langle r \rangle$ of the Floquet eigenphases, by kick and field size, at $\tau = 2.3$ averaged over $\gamma = 1, \dots, 16$. Reference values: Poisson $2 \ln 2 - 1 \approx 0.386$, orthogonal ≈ 0.536 , unitary ≈ 0.603 . Static is Poisson, quadratic is orthogonal, cubic and mixed are unitary.

Figure 2: Mean adjacent-gap ratio of the Floquet eigenphases against field size p , for the static map and the quadratic, cubic, and mixed kicks, with the Poisson, orthogonal, and unitary reference lines. The kick selects the Wigner–Dyson class, and the assignment is stable across field sizes.

Spectral form factor. The spectral form factor $S(k) = \langle |\text{Tr} U_{\gamma,\tau}^k|^2 \rangle / q$, binned in k/q , distinguishes the classes by the shape of the early ramp: the unitary ramp is linear, $S \approx k/q$, the orthogonal ramp is approximately twice as steep at small argument, and the Poisson value is the flat plateau $S \approx 1$. Table 2 reports the binned form factor for each kick against the unitary ramp. The static form factor sits near the Poisson plateau, the cubic and mixed form factors track the unitary ramp, and the quadratic form factor sits at roughly twice the unitary ramp, the orthogonal value. The binned curves are shown in Figure 3.

k/q	unitary ramp k/q	static	quadratic	cubic	mixed
0.025	0.025	0.62	0.048	0.027	0.032
0.075	0.075	1.60	0.152	0.085	0.066
0.125	0.125	0.90	0.235	0.130	0.128

Table 2: Binned spectral form factor $S(k)$ at small k/q , by kick. The cubic and mixed values track the unitary ramp k/q ; the quadratic values sit at roughly twice the unitary ramp, the orthogonal signature; the static values fluctuate near the Poisson plateau $S \approx 1$.

Figure 3: Binned spectral form factor against k/q for the three kicks, with the unitary (linear) and Poisson (plateau) reference curves. The cubic and mixed kicks follow the unitary ramp; the quadratic kick follows the steeper orthogonal ramp.

Time-reversal residual. The symmetry theorem behind the orthogonal assignment is checked directly. Table 3 reports the residual $\|\Theta_\gamma U_{\gamma,\tau} \Theta_\gamma^{-1} - U_{\gamma,\tau}^{-1}\|$ for the candidate time reversal $\Theta_\gamma = D_\gamma PC$. For the quadratic kick the residual is at machine precision, confirming the exact symmetry of Corollary 4.4(i); for the cubic and mixed kicks it is of order one, confirming that this antiunitary is broken. The residual is independent of τ , as it must be for a structural symmetry, with the same values across $\tau \in \{0.8, 1.6, 2.3, 3.0, 4.2\}$.

p	quadratic	cubic	mixed
43	1.1×10^{-14}	1.28	1.31
83	2.2×10^{-14}	1.41	1.41
101	2.6×10^{-14}	1.41	1.41

Table 3: Time-reversal residual $\|\Theta_\gamma U \Theta_\gamma^{-1} - U^{-1}\|$ for $\Theta_\gamma = D_\gamma PC$, at $\tau = 2.3$. The quadratic kick carries the symmetry to machine precision; the cubic and mixed kicks break it. Values are independent of τ .

Parity versus degree. Corollary 4.5 selects the class by the parity of the monomial kick rather than its degree, a distinction the quadratic and cubic kicks alone cannot draw. The quartic and quintic kicks, the next representatives of each parity, separate the two. Table 4 reports the gap ratio and the time-reversal residual for x^2 and x^4 of even degree and x^3 and x^5 of odd degree, over \mathbb{F}_p with $p \in \{43, 83, 101\}$, all larger than the degrees. The even-degree kicks sit at the orthogonal gap ratio and carry the antiunitary $\Theta_\gamma = D_\gamma PC$ to machine precision; the odd-degree kicks sit at the unitary gap ratio and break it. The quartic tracks the quadratic and the quintic tracks the cubic, so the class follows the parity of the degree and not its size, confirming Corollary 4.5 at its first two higher-degree cases.

diagnostic	even degree		odd degree	
	x^2	x^4	x^3	x^5
mean gap ratio	0.540	0.526	0.594	0.589
time-reversal residual	5×10^{-15}	5×10^{-15}	1.37	1.42

Table 4: Gap ratio and time-reversal residual $\|\Theta_\gamma U \Theta_\gamma^{-1} - U^{-1}\|$ for monomial kicks of even and odd degree, averaged over $p \in \{43, 83, 101\}$, $\tau \in \{0.8, 2.3, 4.2\}$, and $\gamma = 1, 2, 3$. Reference gap ratios: orthogonal 0.536, unitary 0.603. The even-degree kicks are orthogonal and carry the time reversal; the odd-degree kicks are unitary and break it. The class follows the parity of the degree.

Operator scrambling. The diagnostic here is the out-of-time-order correlator of a translation under the Floquet evolution, averaged over kick strengths. For the static map this correlator is frozen at unity, since translations commute with \mathcal{K}_q and are conserved; the kick breaks the conservation by Lemma 4.1, and the correlator then scrambles. This translation-sector diagnostic is distinct from the boost-boost correlator of Section 3.2, whose static value is already nontrivial. Table 5 lists the correlator magnitude over the first Floquet steps. The plotted quantity is the correlator magnitude $|F|$, whose late-time value is the finite-size Haar floor: the normalized correlator is an overlap in the traceless operator Hilbert space of dimension $q^2 - 1$, so complete operator spreading gives $\mathbb{E}|F|^2 = (q^2 - 1)^{-1}$, a root-mean-square floor $|F| \sim q^{-1}$, and a squared correlator $|F|^2$ flooring at order q^{-2} . The unitary-class kicks (cubic and mixed) reach this floor in a single step; the orthogonal-class kick (quadratic) reaches it over two to three steps. The unitary class scrambles faster than the orthogonal class, the expected ordering, and the decay is shown in Figure 4.

step	static	quadratic	cubic	mixed
1	1.000	0.095	0.005	0.005
2	1.000	0.027	0.014	0.012
3	1.000	0.015	0.010	0.014
5	1.000	0.012	0.015	0.013

Table 5: Magnitude of the Floquet out-of-time-order correlator over the first steps, by kick. The static correlator is frozen; the cubic and mixed correlators reach the $1/q$ magnitude floor in one step; the quadratic correlator takes two to three steps.

Figure 4: Decay of the Floquet out-of-time-order correlator by kick. The static correlator stays at unity. The unitary-class kicks collapse in one step; the orthogonal-class kick collapses over a few steps.

Robustness in the free-evolution time. The class is not an artifact of the value $\tau = 2.3$. Table 6 reports the gap ratio as τ is scanned over $\{0.8, 1.6, 2.3, 3.0, 4.2\}$, averaged over field sizes and kick strengths. The quadratic kick stays at the orthogonal value and the cubic and mixed kicks stay at the unitary value across the scan.

τ	quadratic	cubic	mixed
0.8	0.539	0.587	0.593
1.6	0.542	0.597	0.594
2.3	0.536	0.590	0.593
3.0	0.522	0.588	0.607
4.2	0.544	0.600	0.575

Table 6: Mean gap ratio against free-evolution time τ , by kick. The orthogonal class of the quadratic kick and the unitary class of the cubic and mixed kicks are stable across τ .

The four diagnostics agree. The gap ratio, the spectral form factor, the time-reversal residual, and the scrambling rate all place the quadratic kick in the orthogonal class and the cubic and mixed kicks in the unitary class, across field sizes and free-evolution times, with the orthogonal assignment carrying the analytic symmetry of Theorem 4.3.

5 Discussion and conclusions

The result is a Wigner–Dyson symmetry class controlled by an arithmetic property of the kick. The static Kloosterman map is integrable, with Poisson level statistics and a non-scrambling, power-law out-of-time-order correlator, the signature of integrable dynamics [3]. A position kick removes the conserved translations of Lemma 4.1, and a reflection symmetry of the kick then selects the symmetry class: a reflection-symmetric kick preserves an affine-parity antiunitary time reversal and places the map in the orthogonal class, while a kick that breaks the affine-parity family places it

in the unitary class. For a monomial kick this reduces to the parity of the degree, established at every degree in Corollary 4.5: even-degree kicks are orthogonal and odd-degree kicks unitary, with the quadratic, cubic, and mixed kicks the cases confirmed by all four diagnostics. The orthogonal selection is fixed by Theorem 4.3; the unitary selection combines the breaking of the complete affine coordinate antiunitary family with the four numerical diagnostics across prime fields.

What the construction adds to the established symmetry-class mechanism of the kicked top and the kicked rotor [4] is the nature of the control parameter. In the kicked top the class is moved by continuous physical couplings; here it is moved by a reflection symmetry of the kick over a finite field, a discrete arithmetic quantity. That the control is arithmetic rather than formal is recorded by the characteristic-three collapse of Section 4.2: the same cubic polynomial realizes a different class over a field of characteristic three, where the absolute trace renders it linear, so the class is fixed by the kick monomial as an object over the specific field and not by its written form. The base operator sits apart from the other finite-dimensional arithmetic quantum systems in the same way. The quantized cat map carries its statistics through a symmetry of a fixed discrete-time map [11, 12]; the Kloosterman Hamiltonian is instead a continuous-time generator, self-adjoint by Proposition 2.2, whose static statistics are Poisson and whose kicked dynamics carry the symmetry-class transition, the arithmetic entering through the kick rather than through the base.

Several questions remain open. The scalar position kicks used here cannot realize the symplectic class: over a prime field the Hilbert space has odd dimension, so no antiunitary on it squares to $-I$ and the symplectic time reversal, which would require $\Theta^2 = -I$, is excluded by Corollary 4.6, leaving the orthogonal and unitary classes as the only possibilities. A symplectic realization would call for an even-rank or quaternionic refinement of the construction, and whether one exists over a Kloosterman base is not known. The class of a general kick beyond the monomial case is open: a monomial kick over a prime field is settled by its degree parity in Corollary 4.5, but the collapse in characteristic three shows that over a non-prime field the effective degree, and with it the class, can depend on the characteristic through the absolute trace, so the rule for a general polynomial kick over an arbitrary finite field is not settled here. The transient scrambling of the kicked correlator, which reaches the finite-size floor within a few Floquet steps, sits between the frozen static correlator and full ergodicity, and a controlled description of that window, together with its relation to the Bessel envelope (8) of the static correlator and to the bound on operator growth [10], is left to future work. Finally, a kick that preserves the affine-parity antiunitary leaves the class unchanged, so a class-preserving kick and a class-breaking kick are distinguished a priori by the criterion (16), and a systematic account of which kicks preserve each class would complete the picture.

Author declarations

Conflict of interest

The author has no conflicts to disclose.

Author contributions

Brandon Yates: Conceptualization; Formal analysis; Investigation; Methodology; Software; Visualization; Writing – original draft; Writing – review and editing.

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20761735>.

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